

JUSTIFICATION OF THE INITIAL PRINCIPLES OF PLANNING THE NEED FOR SPARE PARTS FOR ENGINEERING EQUIPMENT RECOVERY

Baranov A.,

Candidate of Technical Sciences (Ph.D), Associate Professor, associate professor of the Support Forces Tactics Department, Hetman Petro Sahaidachnyi National Army Academy Ukraine, Lviv

Baranov Yu.,

Candidate of Technical Sciences (Ph.D), Associate Professor, professor of the Department of Engineering Equipment, Hetman Petro Sahaidachnyi National Army Academy Ukraine, Lviv

Brychynskiy O.

Senior instructor of the Support Forces Tactics Department, Hetman Petro Sahaidachnyi National Army Academy, Ukraine, Lviv

Mishchenko V.,

Senior instructor of the Support Forces Tactics Department, Hetman Petro Sahaidachnyi National Army Academy Ukraine, Lviv

Burashnikov O.

the Head of the Scientific-research Department (Engineer troops) of the Army Scientific Center, Hetman Petro Sahaidachnyi National Army Academy Ukraine, Lviv

Abstract

Analysis of employment of engineering equipment in the area of the Joint Forces operation, and now – during the Ukrainian-Russian war, indicates an insufficient level of rational distribution and use of spare parts by the troops (forces) repair and recovery bodies. Besides, lack of necessary spare parts leads to long periods of engineering equipment recovery, and as a consequence, the unpreparedness of the engineer unit to perform the assigned tasks.

The article is prepared on a topical issue related to justification of the initial principles of planning the need for spare parts to carry out recovery of engineering equipment, which in turn will allow: to make correct management decisions regarding maintaining a certain level of technical condition of engineering equipment; timely supply of repair units with spare parts; will improve time indicators for recovery of engineering equipment.

Keywords: engineering equipment; technical condition; spare parts.

1. INTRODUCTION.

The main condition for the successful performance of tasks of engineering support for the actions of troops (forces) by the engineer units of the Armed Forces (AF) of Ukraine in the area of the Joint Forces operation (JFO), as well as during the large-scale invasion of the Russian Federation on the territory of Ukraine, is to maintain the combat capability of the engineer units of the Armed Forces of Ukraine according to the level of completeness with engineering equipment (EE) serviceable samples [1; 2].

Formulation of the problem. The experience of the use of engineer units of the Armed Forces of Ukraine in the area of JFO shows that the problem of the availability of spare parts (SP) in repair units has become very acute. The main part of EE has exceeded the limit of its service life, and has also exhausted its resource, which led to the occurrence of failures in the main amount of the equipment [3].

It can also be noted that during JFO, the main source of replenishment of EE losses is its timely recovery. But very often, the lack of the necessary SP leads to long periods of its recovery and, as a result, the engineer unit is unprepared to perform the task as intended. The problem of availability of SP in repair units

is one of the most important, since timely provision or availability of the necessary amount of SP enables repair units to quickly carry out work on recovering the technical condition (TC) of EE, and, accordingly, ensure the effective use as intended.

Analysis of recent research and publications.

When searching for scientific publications in this subject area, one cannot ignore the scientific works of leading scientists (V. Sivak [4], O. Vorobiov [5], B. Demyanchuk [6], O. Volokh [7], P. Openenko [8] and others). The researchers consider increasing of the TC efficiency of military equipment.

However, taking into account the results of the above-mentioned scientific studies and the experience of conducting JFO [9], there is an urgent need to increase the level of efficiency of EE TC recovery by adjusting the need for SP.

Thus, justification of the initial principles of planning the need for spare parts in order to carry out recovery of engineering equipment will allow to make correct management decisions regarding maintaining a certain level of EE TC and timely supply of repair units with SP, as well as to improve time indicators for recovery of EE.

The purpose of the article. Justification of the initial principles of planning the need for SP in order to carry out recovery of EE TC.

2. RESEARCH RESULTS.

It is obvious that today to develop a methodology of planning the need for SP to recover EE TC is of interest, that will allow to solve the following tasks:

- to determine the need for repair units in SP (formation of the necessary nomenclature and the number of SP required to recover EE TC);

- determine the optimal size and periodicity of the order of SP;

- carry out selection of the suppliers of SP;

- to optimize the reserves of SP for recovery of EE TC;

- to form a rational budget for the procurement of SP in the conditions of limited funding and the level of material and technical support.

The conditions in which EE is currently being used have created new problems in the field of providing SP. The lack of reliable operational information regarding EE failures during operation has led to the practical impossibility of applying methods based on the theory of recovery and the theory of operational reliability.

In mathematical statistics, there are two main criteria by which the applicability of a particular mathematical model is evaluated: accuracy and adequacy of the model [10]. Evaluation of models with the help of these criteria must be carried out after calculations of the need for repair units in SP.

When planning the need for SP for recovery of EE TC, it is necessary to formulate initial principles, namely:

- provision of the forecast characteristics of the need for SP;

- compliance with the requirements for initial data;

- compliance with the requirements for models of forecasting the need for SP;

- compliance with the requirements for standard packages of applied computer programs.

The forecast obtained using the selected mathematical model should be characterized by the following factors:

- value (the value of the forecast is determined by the possibility of using its results for planning the activities of repair units);

- reliability (the reliability of the forecast is determined by the reliability of the initial data and the correctly selected model of the phenomenon under study);

- accuracy (accuracy is a criterion of forecast quality [10]);

- timeliness (for prospective planning, prognostic assessments must be received in a timely manner);

- compliance with the specified time interval (forecasts must correspond to the specified time interval, in the conditions of repair units work, it is necessary to receive short-term (monthly) forecasts, that is explained by the specific features of the use of EE samples).

The main initial data for planning the need for SP are the statistics of SP costs for the previous periods of using EE samples (time series of values), as well as

quantitative information about changes in the main factors affecting the need for SP. During the analysis of the initial data, it is determined which initial data are the most relevant while planning the need for SP. When collecting information, the selection of reliable data is carried out, confirmed by the reporting documentation of engineer units. Obtaining forecasts at a given time interval requires a constant sequence of initial data.

The process of ensuring the required level of EE TC is carried out with the aim of:

- maintenance of EE TC at the proper level while performing the assigned tasks;

- rapid recovery of EE TC (close interrelated connection between the need for SP and material and technical support).

In practice, the technically and economically justified supply of repair units with SP is achieved by the necessary level of resource provision, the key stages of which are cost planning and planning of the need for SP, the costs of their acquisition and storage. Currently, it is impossible to make an accurate forecast of the consumption of SP used for EE repair without conducting a prior detailed analysis of the current state of the EE sample, as well as taking into account the main significant factors that affect the process of using SP during the entire life of EE.

EE consists of recovery systems, the serviceability of which is maintained during its service life by performing EE recovery, with the aim of preventing and eliminating failures, repairing or replacing failed parts and assemblies. Accordingly, during the operation of EE samples, parts and assemblies are repeatedly replaced. Failure of parts and assemblies is a random event, and the probabilistic characteristics of parts resource dispersion are described by various distribution laws, which are determined by methods of mathematical statistics. The failure of parts and assemblies that occur during EE operation is eliminated by replacing faulty parts with new SP. With all types of EE or its component units repair, replacement of SP is carried out depending on the various intensity of failures of parts and assemblies. At the same time, the costs of purchasing SP depend not only on the frequency of SP replacements, but also on their market cost.

Also, the following working hypotheses and theoretical prerequisites must be adopted when planning the need for SP for EE TC recovery:

- 1) the planning of the need for SP during the EE service life in real operating conditions should: be based on reliability indicators, which are determined by the results of actual replacements of EE parts and assemblies in real operating conditions; be considered in stages, that is, according to the cycles of operation and types of EE repair;

- 2) the moment of the part, assembly or EE component unit limit state onset, is a random event (that is, there is a dispersion of resources compared to their average values);

- 3) EE parts, assemblies or EE component units are fully functional until they fail, after that they become completely inoperable. The tasks of replacing parts due to the gradual deterioration of the elements perfor-

mance or due to the gradual increase in the cost of storage are excluded;

4) queuing problems, which arise due to the fact that several elements have failed at the same time, and the means of repair are limited are not taken into account;

5) to simplify the calculations, it is accepted that when a recovered part is put into operation, the parameter of its fault-free operation duration corresponds to the new SP.

Any technical system, including EE, is characterized by a certain structure. That is, it is a set of elements that ensure the normal performance of the working functions of the entire system. In the process of operation, parts, assemblies and component units of EE samples lose their efficiency, that leads to failure or reaching the limit state of the system as a whole [2, 11]. To restore the EE IT, it is necessary to replace the defective part with a spare one, or repair it. From the point of view of SP use, we will consider only the replacement of parts and SP. Thus, in order to maintain the required level of EE IT during operation in the situation of parts, assemblies and component units failure for various reasons, their permanent replacement with SP takes place. It is obvious that in order to determine the characteristics of the change in the number of replacements of parts during the working life of EE, it is necessary to analyze the sequence of replacements of SP by time intervals or by intervals of working time.

A part that has been used since the beginning of EE operation during a random period of time, that is conventionally equal to the average resource of a new part, fails and is replaced by a new (spare) part.

A SP, which has worked for a random period of time, that is conventionally equal to the SP average resource, also fails and is replaced by another SP, etc.

Thus, in the process of EE operation, in order to constantly maintain the TC at a given level, the parts that have failed must be constantly replaced. If such a sequence of replacements is considered for the entire service life of EE until it reaches its limit state, then the latter can be represented in the form of a flow of SP replacements, caused by a flow of failures of EE parts, assemblies and component units [12]. If we look at a fairly long period of time, then with a high probability it can be stated that there will be a need for almost any type of SP. Therefore, to date, the question concerning SP which will be necessary during this period of time, and whether it is advisable to purchase them for preliminary storage, remains unresolved.

For effective inventory management, it is important to choose a reasonable method of forecasting. For this purpose, categories of short-term, medium-term and long-term forecasts are often used. Thus, when forecasting consumer demand for SP, in many cases a forecast of up to 6 months is considered short-term, from 6 months to 2 years - medium-term, and more than 2 years, respectively, long-term.

3. CONCLUSIONS AND PROSPECTS OF FURTHER RESEARCH.

In this way, the principles of planning the needs for SP to recover EE TC have been considered. When

planning the need for SP to recover EE TC, it is necessary to take into account:

which elements of the SP nomenclature are subject to forecasting;

how far into the future the forecast should be made (days, weeks, months, quarters, years);

how often the forecast should be carried out (the possibility of automating the forecasting process);

what the tolerable prediction error is.

A large number of factors influence the emergence of a need for this or that SP. Therefore, the task of planning the need for SP can be conventionally divided into two stages. At the first stage, during the analysis of factors, the variables that correlate with the need for SP are revealed. During the second stage, the dependence of the need for SP on selected factors is analyzed, and a forecast for the future period of time is made. When planning the needs for SP, it is necessary to possess information that characterizes, in fact, the SP itself:

1) the catalog number of the SP is the number that identifies the part in the technical documentation. It should be noted that in some cases one and the same SP may be indicated in the technical documentation under different catalog numbers. Such variety of catalog numbers is due to the fact that the manufacturer places in the catalog number information about the application of the SP. For example, one and the same SP can have a range of different catalog numbers, by number for different EE samples;

2) the cost of the SP - in this case, we will understand the inventory cost of the SP;

3) the cost of storage and delivery - these parameters allow to estimate the costs of storage and delivery of SP. To determine the cost of delivery and storage, it is necessary to have the characteristics of mass and external dimensions of the SP. It should also be noted that the conditions of SP delivery and storage are not constant, and may change over time (this is affected by the cost of transportation, rental of premises, etc.).

References

1. Methodical guide on the organization and conduct of seasonal service of weapons and military equipment in military units and subunits, that perform tasks in the ATO area, areas of combat capability restoration. – Kyiv: the Ground Forces Command of the Armed Forces of Ukraine. 2015. – 22 p.
2. Baranov A., Baranov Yu., Kalenyk M., Nagachevskyi V., Konturov V. Organization of military equipment maintenance based on combat experience. The scientific heritage: VOL 1. 2022. №98. C. 73–75.
3. Baranov Yu. Influence of maintenance and recovery processes on management efficiency of military equipment technical condition in the Armed Forces of Ukraine. Yu. Baranov, A. Baranov, I. Martyniuk, S. Kovalchuk, S. Shpak. The scientific heritage: VOL 1. 2023. №105(105). P. 90–92.2.
4. Sivak V.A. Fundamentals of car production and repair technology: Training manua. Khmelnytsky: NA PVU, 2003. 143 p.
5. Vorobiov O.M. Methods of rational structure substantiation and use of forces and means of engineering troops equipment repair in the defense operation of

AC JRRF in the process of its recovery: Thesis ... Candidate of Technical Sciences: 20.02.14. Kamyianets-Podilskyi, 2005. 217 p.

6. Demyanchuk B.O. Automotive support of subunits and units in different conditions of environment and warfare. Part 1. Training manual. Odessa: VA Publishing House, 2014. 262 p.

7. Volokh O.P. Methodology for substantiating the rational values of parameters for maintenance of engineering weapons while using them as intended: Thesis ... Candidate of Technical Sciences: 20.02.14/ Kamyianets-Podilskyi, 2007. 175 p.

8. Openko P.V. Methodology for predicting the durability of anti-aircraft missile troops armament while operating according to technical condition: Thesis ... Candidate of Technical Sciences: 20.02.14. Kyiv, 2013. 203 p.

9. Baranov A., Baranov Yu., Korolov O., Maliuk V., Brychynskyi O. Analysis of the current state of engineer vehicles and equipment and peculiarities of their maintenance and repair system functioning. The scientific heritage: VOL 1. 2022. №100. C. 67–69.

10. Shuenkin V.A., Donchenko V.S. Applied models of queuing theory. Kyiv: NMK VO, 1992. 397p.

11. Baranov Yu.M. Management of the technical condition of military equipment and justification of its quality indicators. Yu.M. Baranov, V.I. Kryvtsun, G.B. Zhiron, L.V. Solodeeva. Collection of scientific works of the Military Institute of Kyiv National University. 2017. No. 55. P. 52–61.

12. Sysoev O.O. Problems, tendencies and prospects of development of the system of technical support of troops (forces) in wars and armed conflicts of the late 20th - early 21st centuries. Kyiv: NDUU, 2004. 39 p.